

Methane enrichment in psychrophilic anaerobic digestion of pig slurry by using iron zero-valent nanoparticles

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Abstract: Anaerobic digestion at ambient temperature is an alternative for low-cost anaerobic digesters to be implemented at rural areas, although lower methane production rates are expected compared to mesophilic or thermophilic temperature operations. Thus, strategies to enhance methane production at psychrophilic temperature are needed. The aim of this study is to examine the effects of nano zero-valent iron (nZVI) dosage onto anaerobic digestion of pig slurry in psychrophilic temperature operation in lab-scale batch and continuous assays. First, different doses of nZVI (0, 42, 84, and 168 mg g_{VS}^{-1}) were tested in batch assays, establishing that the dose of 84 mg g_{VS}^{-1} achieved the highest enhancement in methane production compared to the control (71%). The 84 mg g_{VS}^{-1} dose of nZVI was tested in a 6 L anaerobic digester operated in continuous mode for 320 days, in 5 different phases with different nZVI addition strategies. Methane content in biogas achieved a maximum of 81% when adding a weekly pulse of nZVI of 84 mg g_{VS}^{-1} , compared to 69% with no nZVI addition. Although biogas production decreased 24% when nZVI were added to the reactor, it still can be a valuable method to upgrade biogas in psychrophilic anaerobic digestion.

Keywords: biogas; up-grading; inhibition; low-cost digester; rural digester

Introduction

Livestock production in 2021 was 142 million pigs, 76 million bovine animals, 60 million sheep and 11 million goats in the European Union (Spain accounted for 24% of the EU's pigs, 9% of the EU's bovines, 25% of the EU's sheep and 23% of the EU's goats), generating approximately 55 billion tonnes of manure (Nagarajan et al., 2023). In this context, livestock manure should be considered as a resource rather than waste as it has an abundance of available nutrients for crops, carbon for bioenergy production and can promote soil carbon stocks. In terms of greenhouse gases (GHG) and ammonia (NH_3) emissions, agriculture and livestock are by far the largest emitting sectors with total NH_3 emissions amounting to approximately 3.5 million tonnes a year, more than 90% of total ammonia emitted in the EU27+UK. Several approaches have been suggested and evaluated for reducing emissions from excreted animal manure. Among others, covering manure storage tanks with an air-tight membrane represent a good and economic strategy since it avoids the release of emissions while induces anaerobic digestion of the stored manure if the microbial community can acclimate to ambient conditions (Kupper et al., 2020). When using physical covers, it is necessary to capture the gases and further process/recover to not release when slurry is later managed (e.g., fertilization). It should be considered that the promotion of anaerobic digestion will lead to an increase of biogas production that cannot be released to the atmosphere. It is compulsory to use it or ultimately burn it in a flare to limit its greenhouse effect. In this sense, anaerobic digestion (AD) is a well-established and widely implemented technology in the European agricultural sector for treating livestock manure since it generates a renewable fuel in the form of biogas, improves manure fertilizer quality, and reduces odours, pathogens as well as greenhouse gas emissions (Awasthi et al., 2022; Torrellas et al., 2018).

The promotion of the AD in covered ponds, at low temperatures (<20 °C, psychrophilic conditions), could represent an economically viable alternative since,

on the one hand, methane (CH₄) can be recovered and valorised in the form of thermal and/or electrical energy and, in the other hand, it does not require additional thermal energy input as occurs in the mesophilic (35 °C) and thermophilic (55 °C) anaerobic digestion processes. However, temperature affects AD and biomethanation due to the dependence of methanogens growth on this factor. Decreases in temperature inactivates methanogens, thus reducing methane yields, due to alteration in membrane fluidity that inhibits substrate transport across the cell membrane. At low temperatures, high methane solubility results in lower gas phase methane concentrations and shifting of the microbial community structure towards acetoclastic methanogenesis causes lower methane yields. In addition, mass transfer limitations due to an increase in substrate viscosity, and an increase in membrane fouling are additional causes of low methane productivity in cold environments (Dev et al., 2019). Nevertheless, King et al. (2011) studied in-storage psychrophilic anaerobic digestion of swine manure confirming that an acclimated microbial community is developed within 1-2 years.

The enhancement of methane production in anaerobic digestion is a subject of constant research, and several technologies and techniques can be applied (Li et al., 2019). The application of nanoparticles (NPs) is receiving increasing attention as a strategy to increase methane production in anaerobic digestion. NPs could act as electron donors or acceptors, and cofactor of important enzymes in various bioprocesses, enhancing their yields (Dehghani et al., 2019). The enhancement of methane content in biogas in mesophilic and thermophilic anaerobic digestion has been previously reported when using sewage sludge and pig slurry supplemented with nano zero-valent iron (nZVI) (Barrena et al., 2021; Cerrillo et al., 2021), so it could be also a good strategy to improve methane production rate at psychrophilic temperature conditions. It has been reported that the production of biogas is also enhanced by nZVI addition (Abdelsalam et al., 2017). Although the increasing amount of published research on the impacts of NPs on AD, most of the nZVI studies focused on batch and short-term assays, using waste activated sludge, and only a few used a high strength wastewater such as livestock manure as a substrate (Huang et al., 2019), and none of them worked at psychrophilic temperature range.

The aim of this study is to examine the effects of nZVI dosage onto methane production in anaerobic digestion of pig slurry at lab-scale batch assays and on long term and continuously fed assays at psychrophilic temperature condition.

Material and Methods

Two set-ups were used to investigate the effect of the addition of nZVI. First, batch assays were performed to find the optimum concentration of nZVI using 1.2 L serum bottles in triplicate. These serum bottles were filled with a 500 g solution comprised of the inoculum (5 g_{VSS} L⁻¹), pig slurry as substrate (5 g_{COD} L⁻¹) and the different concentrations of nZVI (0, 42, 84, and 168 mg g_{VSS}⁻¹). The bottles were sealed with rubber stoppers and capped with aluminium crimp caps. The headspace was purged with N₂ for 5 min in order to remove O₂. The bottles were incubated at 22±1 °C for 54 days. Methane production was monitored periodically taking a gas sample (0.1 mL) from the headspace with a syringe and analysing the gas composition by gas chromatography, equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD).

Second, a lab-scale continuous stirred tank reactor (6 L) was used for long term experiments, operated for 320 days in 5 different phases (Table 1) in psychrophilic

temperature range in an air-conditioned room (22 ± 1 °C). The reactor was fed in a continuous mode with raw pig slurry during 65 days with a hydraulic retention time of 20 days and an organic loading rate of $2.15 \text{ kg}_{\text{COD}} \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (Phase 0). For the following 55 days (Phase 1) a pulse of nZVI of $84 \text{ mg g}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ was injected per week, according to previous batch assays results. In Phase 2 the same dose was applied to the reactor, but divided in two pulses each week, for other 63 days. In Phase 4, the dose was reduced to $42 \text{ mg g}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ in a pulse per week, for 40 days. And finally, in Phase 4, NP addition was stopped for 100 days. The pig slurry used to feed the reactor was diluted with tap water to obtain the desired organic load. The main characteristics of the diluted pig slurry were as follows: total solids (TS), $36\pm 13 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$; volatile solids (VS), $23\pm 9 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$; total chemical oxygen demand (TCOD), $44\pm 10 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$; total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), $2.8\pm 0.6 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$; ammonia nitrogen, $2.0\pm 0.4 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$. Biogas production was monitored, and methane content was analysed along the assay in the same way as in batch assays. Chemical oxygen demand (COD), ammonium nitrogen ($\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$), total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), total and volatile solids (TS, VS), total and volatile solids (TS, VS) and pH, were determined according to Standard Methods 5220 (APHA, 2012). For both set-ups, nZVI was synthesized following the methodology described by Choe et al. (2001).

Table 1. Operation phases of the psychrophilic anaerobic digestion, number of pulses injected per week and concentration of nZVI of each pulse.

Phase	Period (d)	Frequency of nZVI injection (times/week)	nZVI concentration of the pulse ($\text{mg}_{\text{NP}} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ SV}_{\text{added}}$)
0	65	0	0
1	55	1	84
2	63	2	42
3	40	1	42
4	100	0	0

Results and Discussion

In batch assays, accumulated methane production was 164.07, 191.85, 280.07 and $159.69 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ in the vials where 0, 42, 84 and $168 \text{ mg}_{\text{nZVI}} \text{ g}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ had been added, respectively (Figure 1). Thus, the highest methane production increase was of 71% with the dose of $84 \text{ mg}_{\text{nZVI}} \text{ g}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$, also increasing methane content in biogas to 82% (61% with no nZVI addition). The dose of $168 \text{ mg}_{\text{NP}} \text{ g}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ showed an inhibition of methane production, with a reduction of 3% compared to the control. The specific methane production with the dose of $84 \text{ mg}_{\text{NP}} \text{ g}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ is higher than the values reported for batch anaerobic digestion of pig slurry at mesophilic and thermophilic temperature ranges, 267.6 and $235.0 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$, respectively (Cerrillo et al., 2021), making psychrophilic anaerobic digestion supplemented with nZVI an interesting alternative for low-cost rural digesters.

Figure 1. Specific methane production and maximum methane content in biogas of the batch assays performed in psychrophilic temperature conditions with different nZVI dosages.

Long term continuous assays in psychrophilic temperature conditions have shown a clear enhancement in methane content in biogas when nZVI was added. Average methane content in biogas increased from 69%, with no nZVI addition, to an average of 75% in Phase 1, that increased further in Phase 2, with an average of 79% and a maximum of 82% (Figure 2). However, a reduction of 24% in biogas production was detected, producing a slightly decrease in methane production from $0.18 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$ to $0.16 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$, despite the methane percentage increase. This effect may be related to microbial activity inhibition, and further research is needed. When the nZVI dose was reduced by half in Phase 3, methane percentage began to decrease, and the suppression of nZVI pulses (Phase 4) returned methane percentage and biogas production to values similar to those obtained in Phase 0.

Figure 1 Biogas methane content in Phase 0 (no nZVI addition), Phase 1 (dose of nZVI of $84 \text{ mg g}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ per week), Phase 2 (same dose but divided in 2 pulses per week), Phase 3 (dose of nZVI of $42 \text{ mg g}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ per week) and Phase 4 (no NP addition).

Previous assays of nZVI addition to anaerobic digestion of pig slurry in mesophilic and thermophilic temperature ranges showed a fast increase in methane content in biogas (Cerrillo et al., 2021), as reported in this study, but also a long-lasting effect after stopping nZVI addition, which has not been observed in psychrophilic temperature range.

Conclusions

The addition of nZVI in psychrophilic temperature range in anaerobic digestion has shown a clear increase in biogas methane content. In batch assays, the highest methane production increase was of 71% with the dose of 84 mg_{nZVI} g_{VS}⁻¹, also increasing methane content in biogas to 82% (61% with no nZVI addition). In continuous assays, methane content was also increased, with a maximum of 82% when a pulse of 42 mg_{nZVI} g_{VS}⁻¹ was injected in the reactor twice a week (61% with no nZVI addition). However, differently from batch assays, a decrease of 24% in biogas production was detected in the long term, which may be related to microbial activity inhibition. Despite this effect, nanoparticles addition still can be a valuable method to upgrade biogas in psychrophilic anaerobic digestion to boost low-cost reactors implementation in rural areas.

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